

IMPLEMENTATION OF EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION IN THE ERA OF GLOBALIZATION IN INCREASING TEACHER PROFESSIONALITY IN PRIVATE MADRASAH IBTIDAIYAH THARIQUL JANNAH PANGALENGAN BANDUNG DISTRICT

RICKY YOSEPTRY ¹, ANDRI FERIYANSYAH ² and META ROSTIANI ³

^{1,2,3} Universitas Islam Nusantara, Bandung, Indonesia.

E-Mail: ¹rickyoseptry@uninus.ac.id, ²andriferiyansyah@uninus.ac.id, ³metarostiani@uninus.ac.id

Abstract

This research is based on the G20 on Education and Culture Kick Off event, Nadiem Anwar Makarim as Minister of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (Mendikbudristek) Indonesia said that there were four priority goals of the Education Working Group, namely quality universal education, digital technology in education, solidarity and partnership, and the post-Covid-19 world of work. The specific objectives of this research are as follows: 1) To find out how educational organizations plan in the era of globalization in increasing teacher professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan; 2) To find out how education is organized in the era of globalization in increasing teacher professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan; 3) To find out how educational organizations are implemented in the era of globalization in increasing teacher professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan; 4) To find out how supervision of educational organizations in the era of globalization increases teacher professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan. This research was carried out at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan Bandung District, using the research method used was a qualitative descriptive method. The general conclusion in this research is that MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan in implementing educational organizations in the era of globalization uses HR management to improve teacher professionalism. The management functions used in management include planning, organizing, implementing and supervising. In practice, there are still many shortcomings so that not all existing teachers are able to adapt and have competence in the era of globalization. So educational organizations need to implement appropriate management to overcome this problem.

Keywords: Organization, Education, Globalization, Professional.

INTRODUCTION

Negative Middle School Teachers Nowadays, Indonesia has entered a new era in the field of education. At the G20 On Education and Culture Kick Off event, Nadiem Anwar Makarim as Minister of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (Mendikbudristek) Indonesia said that there were four priority goals of the Education Working Group, namely quality universal education, digital technology in education, solidarity and partnerships, as well as the post-Covid-19 world of work.

Then from that, 2016 was the beginning of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 which was marked by the development of the Digital Economy, Big Data, IoT (Internet of Things), Robotics, Cloud Systems, all of which are technology-based until now. Moreover, Indonesia has a goal of pushing its economy to become the 10 largest country by 2030. The cause of this rapid change is due to the implications of globalization.

In the chronology of globalization, at least 3 stages have occurred in the development of globalization. In the first stage, globalization occurred in the political field, marked by the formation of the United Nations (UN) in 1945. Thirty years later around the mid-1970s, the second stage occurred, namely economic globalization, marked by free trade and the formation of economic cooperation such as AFTA and APEC. Then, thirty years later or mid-2000, the third stage of globalization in the field of culture was marked by the nations of the world moving towards a large culture to be shared together, as well as the increasingly fading local cultural identity (Kompas edition 14, November 2004) . From this chronology, it can be estimated that thirty years later from the mid-2000s, namely in 2035, a new stage of globalization will occur, most likely globalization in the field of education.

Terminologically, the term globalization of education is not yet popular in society because globalization of education has not yet occurred and globalization also refers to all aspects of life. These aspects of life are interconnected with each other without recognizing national boundaries or primordial ties such as ethnicity, race and nation. If based on such an understanding of globalization, then globalization of education can be formulated as the practice of organizing, teaching, training and supervising education without recognizing a country's borders. This means that other countries are free to establish an institution in another country or vice versa. This is a fundamental problem in the implementation of education in Indonesia. From this, a question then arises, "Is Indonesia able to compete in the globalization of education?"

The problems that will occur in the globalization of education need to be prepared from now. Practically, this is the task of all groups, from the government, education stakeholders to managers or school principals, educators, students and others. In this regard, if the government is the party who makes decisions or regulations, then a school principal is the person who executes them in the field. This is directly related to new educational management practices in each school.

In the practice of management in schools, we already know that educational administration experts have formulated groups of educational substances, including, (1) curriculum or learning; (2) student affairs; (3) staffing; (4) facilities and infrastructure; (5) finance; and (6) community environment. In this research we tried to focus on the third group, namely personnel management.

Employees (Educators and Education Personnel) in any institution are the most vital position. It is recognized that costs are important, infrastructure and technology are needed. However, the availability of human resources (HR) who are not competent in handling this will make all of this useless.

On December 3 2018, the Ministry of Education and Culture released the results of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). The competency scores of students in Indonesia in the fields of Literacy, Numeracy and Science are lower than similar measurements in the previous 3 years. In fact, this value is equivalent to the results achieved in 2000.

The results of global measurements for students aged 15 years show that the average score of Indonesian students is 371 in reading, mathematics 379, and science 396. This score is below the average of 79 PISA participating countries, namely 487 for reading ability, and 489 for math and science ability. What was even more surprising was that the poor results of students' literacy skills in PISA 2018 were quite surprising to many parties, especially because they occurred after the School Literacy Movement (GLS) had been promoted since 2016.

From the PISA report it is also known that the low quality of educators and disparities in the quality of education in Indonesia are thought to be the main causes of poor literacy skills of students in general.

PISA released the results of its study on the 5 qualities of educators in Indonesia which hinder students' learning, namely, (1) Educators do not understand students' learning needs; (2) Educators are often absent; (3) Educators tend to resist change; (4) Educators do not prepare lessons well; (5) Educators are not flexible in the learning process.

From the facts above, this is a very hard slap in the face of Indonesian education. Educators who are supposed to be people who educate, teach, guide, direct, train, assess and evaluate students are far from adequate. Likewise for a school manager or principal, there needs to be reform in improving the quality of human resources.

This article is designed to present how the implementation of educational organizations is directly related to globalization. Included in this study is an analysis of new educational organizational practices, especially personnel management (human resources, HR) at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Management

Management is a science that is really needed by a manager in managing the company he leads to achieve predetermined goals. Ricky W. Griffin (2016:4) argues that: "Management is a set of activities (including planning and decision making, organizing, leading, and controlling) directed an organization human, financial, physical, and information resources) with the aim of achieving organizational goals in an efficient and effective manner".

The above states that management is a process of planning, organizing, coordinating and controlling resources to achieve targets effectively and efficiently. Effective means that goals can be achieved according to planning, while efficient means that existing tasks are carried out correctly, organized and according to schedule.

Based on the definition above, it can be concluded that management is very important for an organization, and management itself is a process of utilizing organizational resources which consists of the actions of planning, organizing, directing, controlling, effectively and efficiently, in order to achieve the goals set by the company/agency.

2. Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management is the science and art of managing the relationships and roles of the workforce so that they are effective and efficient in helping to realize organizational goals. Management that regulates the human element is often called personnel management or personnel management which is applied to a company to achieve the desired goals.

Mondy (2016:25) states that "Human resource management (HRM) is the use of individuals to achieve organizational objectives". Human resource management (HRM) is the use of individuals to achieve organizational goals. Basically, all managers get things done through the efforts of others. As a result, managers at every level must pay attention to human resource management. Individuals when dealing with other individuals will face many challenges, from an ever-changing workforce to ever-present government regulations, technological and economic revolutions. Furthermore, global competition has forced both large and small organizations to be more conscious of costs and productivity. Due to the critical nature of human resource issues, they should receive primary attention from a manager.

Human resource management, or abbreviated as HRM, is the utilization of a number of individuals efficiently and effectively and can be used optimally to achieve organizational or company goals. HRM studies combine several fields of science such as psychology, sociology, and others. The main element of HRM is humans.

It can be concluded that Human Resource Management is the science and art of managing the relationships and roles of the workforce so that they are effective and efficient and is the most important asset and has skills, encouragement, power and work that are developed optimally in the world of work of a company or organization. to achieve a goal.

3. Professional Teacher

Law number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, in article 1 paragraph 1 states that: Teachers are professional educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing and evaluating students in early childhood education, formal, primary education and secondary education.

From this article, a general understanding can be formulated that a teacher is a person who is responsible for the development of all students' potential, including affective potential, cognitive potential and psychomotor potential.

As for Professionalism in law number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, in article 1 paragraph 4 states that: Professionalism is work or activities carried out by someone and becomes a source of income for life which requires skills, abilities or abilities that meet quality standards or certain norms and requires professional education.

Wojowasito (1982: 162) From a linguistic perspective (etymology), the term professionalism comes from English profession, which means position, job, livelihood, someone who has expertise. Apart from that, Drs. Petersalim (2004:92) in the contemporary language dictionary defines the word profession as a field of work that is based on education and certain skills.

Thus, the word profession can literally be interpreted as a job that requires certain skills and expertise, where these skills and expertise are obtained from special education or training.

Then the word profession gets the suffix *ism*, which in Indonesian means characteristic. So the term Professionalism means the qualities that every professional must have in carrying out his work so that the work can be carried out or carried out as well as possible, with full responsibility for what he has done based on the education and skills he has.

From the meaning or definition of "professionalism" and "teacher" above, it can be concluded that a professional teacher means a characteristic that must be present in a teacher in carrying out his work so that the teacher can carry out his work with full responsibility and is able to develop his skills without interfering with his duties. principal teacher.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method is a method used to obtain data that suits your needs. In this research, the method used is the descriptive method.

Sukmadinata (2017: 72) believes that descriptive research is a type of research that aims to describe or explain existing phenomena, both natural phenomena and man-made phenomena, which can include activities, characteristics, changes, relationships, similarities and differences between one phenomenon and another. .

As has been stated, this research is descriptive in nature, that is, it is only limited to an attempt to reveal a problem, situation or event as it relates to research problems in the application of educational organizations in the era of globalization in increasing teacher professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan.

A research approach is a method or scientific way to obtain data with a specific useful purpose (Darmadi Hamid, 2014, p. 153). In another view, Sukandarrumidi explains that the research approach is the main method used by researchers to achieve goals and determine answers to the problems posed (Sukandarrumidi, 2012, p. 111).

A research approach is the whole method or activity in research starting from formulating the problem to making a conclusion. There are two kinds of research approaches, namely quantitative approaches and qualitative approaches. The quantitative approach means that the information or data presented is in the form of numbers, while the qualitative approach means that the information or data presented is in the form of statements. The qualitative approach is an approach that is also called an investigative approach because researchers usually collect data by meeting face to face and interacting with people at the research site.

Based on the description stated above, it can be concluded that this research uses a qualitative approach because all data obtained is in the form of interviews and face-to-face results. This research is a type of research based on case studies.

The data collection techniques in this research are:

1. Observation

Many thought experts in the field of education have formulated the meaning of observation, one of whom is Sutrisno, (2004: 136) states that: Observation is intended as systematic observation and recording of the phenomena being investigated. Or in other words, the methods of expressing data are carried out by observing and recording the symptoms being investigated. Regarding this observation, the author uses a framework of factors that are arranged or categorized first. According to Subagyo (2004: 63), observation is observations carried out deliberately, systematically regarding social phenomena with psychological symptoms and then recorded. Observation as a data collection tool can be carried out spontaneously, or with a prepared checklist. The purpose of observation is to describe the setting being studied, the activities taking place, the people involved in the activity, and the meaning of the event as seen from the perspective of those seen in the observed event. One of the important, but often forgotten, things in observation is observing things that don't happen.

2. Interview

Interviews are carried out by creating an atmosphere in such a way that informants do not feel that they are being used as research subjects. In this qualitative research, the interview techniques used are unstructured interviews and directed interviews or focused interviews and non-directed interviews or free interviews. Undirected interviews are conducted by researchers so that informants have the freedom and opportunity to express their thoughts, views and feelings without being regulated by the researcher. This technique is used by researchers to obtain detailed information.

Structured interviews are used as a data collection technique, if the researcher or data collector knows exactly what information will be obtained. Therefore, in conducting interviews, data collectors have prepared research instruments in the form of written questions for which alternative answers have also been prepared. The informant in this research was Mr. Ade Jalaludin, S.Pd.I. MM.Pd. with the position of Head of Madrasah MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan.

3. Documentation Study

Documentation is a way of collecting data to produce important notes related to the problem being studied, so that complete, valid data will be obtained and not based on Basrowi's thoughts (2008: 158). The researcher archives the results of the interview, so that the data the researcher creates is in accordance with existing evidence and documentation. And makes it easier for researchers to solve problems that researchers will face. Document study is a complement to the use of observation and interview methods in qualitative research.

In this documentation the researcher collected some data received from MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan.

In this research, the location chosen was MIS Thariqul Jannah which is located at Kp. Lamajang, RT.004/RW.005 Lamajang Village, Pangalengan District, Bandung Regency, West Java Province. The reason for choosing this research location is because MIS Thariqul Jannah is a school under the Ministry of Religion which focuses on acculturation of religion, technology and culture, which is something new in the madrasa environment.

In research that uses a qualitative approach, the population and sample are not known as in quantitative research because the research starts from the case of the existence of individuals or groups in certain social situations and the results only apply to that social situation.

According to Arikunto (2016:26) the research subject is to define the research subject as an object, thing or person to which the data for the research variable is attached, and which is at issue. In research, the research subject has a very strategic role because the research subject is data about the variables that the researcher observes.

In qualitative research, the research subject is referred to as an informant, namely a person who provides information about the data the researcher wants related to the research being carried out. The main subject (key informant) in this research is Mr. Ade Jalaludin S.Pd.I., MM.Pd. as principal of MIS Tariqul Jannah School.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Research Results

After all the necessary data has been gathered completely, the next step is to carry out an analysis of the data that has been collected. This research compares data originating from the field with literature data in the form of theories and concepts that have relevance as assessment standards. Data that has been obtained through observations, interviews and documentation studies, this research is described and grouped based on research questions.

This research also functions as an answer to the research questions posed based on the results of the problems studied starting from planning, organizing, implementing and supervising educational organizations that focus on human resource management as an effort to increase teacher professionalism in the era of globalization. The findings obtained from the results of this research are as follows:

a. Educational Organization Planning in the Era of Globalization in Increasing Teacher Professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan

Educational Organization Planning in the Era of Globalization in Increasing Teacher Professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan is carried out at the beginning of the school year, namely at the beginning of the year meeting which is attended by foundations, committees, madrasa heads, educators and education staff. In this meeting, plans will be formulated for what the madrasah will do for one year. In relation to human resource management in the era of globalization, the school principal will plan activities to be implemented this academic year based on evaluations from the previous year.

An example of this planning is the holding of technology-based learning media guidance for teachers who are less competent in this matter. This was planned because in the previous year (covid period) many senior teachers were not able to carry out online learning. Another reason for carrying out this planning is to anticipate rapid globalization. The principal believes that when a teacher cannot adapt to change, he will be eliminated from the global competition in education. This is also directly related to teacher professionalism in professional competence, namely mastery of technology and communication as well as self-development.

Another thing that the school principal does is that prospective teachers who will enter and teach at MIS Thariqul Jannah must be undergraduate graduates with educational qualifications and be able to master technology. This must be proven by a diploma and a probationary period of 3 months teaching.

So it can be seen whether prospective teachers are suitable or not suitable to teach at school.

Apart from that, learning planning is also required to use technology, one of which is using a laptop or cellphone. The school emphasizes teachers who can use these tools to collaborate learning with technology. For example, using infocus, power point, audio learning, visual learning, audio visual learning or others. As for teachers who cannot yet, they are required to learn from teachers who can use it.

b. Organizing Educational Organizations in the Era of Globalization in Increasing Teacher Professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan

In organizing, the school principal will distribute teaching duties to teachers. This is adjusted to the qualifications held by the teacher, either in terms of individual ability or educator certification.

The problem that arises in organizing is that there are teachers who are not yet able to use technology so that learning will feel monotonous, especially senior teachers. Therefore, the principal uses team teaching techniques, namely one class will be taught by two teachers. One senior teacher is more experienced and the other is a junior teacher who is more versed in technology.

This is considered effective because it will create a mutualistic symbiosis, namely senior teachers learn to use technology in learning from junior teachers, and junior teachers learn from the experiences of senior teachers in learning.

c. Implementation of Educational Organizations in the Era of Globalization in Increasing Teacher Professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan

In its implementation, MIS Thariqul Jannah routinely holds technical guidance every year or provides technical guidance for teachers who need it. For example, in July 2022, the madrasah involved teachers in technology-based learning guidance in Lembang held by the District Ministry of Education. Bandung. There were also teachers who took part in the ANBK and AKMI technical guidance last year so they could teach or provide an overview to students about ANBK and AKMI.

Technological advances make it easier for teachers to teach and students to learn. One implementation is that schools support and facilitate teachers to create learning content on YouTube. Because MIS Thariqul Jannah has had a YouTube channel since 2017. This channel is used to document all activities and provide learning for students.

During learning, teachers do not only look for learning resources from books. The school emphasizes finding relevant learning resources from the internet and applying them in class. As one example, when learning the History of Islamic Culture (SKI), students who previously wrote a lot and listened to the teacher explained that currently the SKI teacher always uses audio-visual learning in the form of Islamic history videos related to the lesson.

d. Supervision of Educational Organizations in the Era of Globalization in Increasing Teacher Professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan

In supervision, the principal routinely carries out supervision to measure teacher performance. This is done to determine whether the teacher is carrying out his duties effectively and efficiently or not. In relation to globalization, school principals will see whether the results of technical guidance or training on technology are used effectively and efficiently in learning so that the output is increased teacher competence and the outcome is that students become more active in learning. For example, one of the teachers who takes the technology-based learning guidance will see how he teaches in class. The results of this supervision will be used as an evaluation and follow-up in the following year. Meanwhile, if the teacher has achieved the goals set by the school, he will be given an award. Likewise, if it is not optimal then it will be used as a reference for madrasa planning next year.

2. Discussion

a. Educational Organization Planning in the Era of Globalization in Increasing Teacher Professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan

Human resource planning is very important for the interests of individual employees, because planning can help increase their potential, as well as employee satisfaction can be achieved through career planning. Apart from that, human resource planning is very important for organizations in obtaining prospective employees who meet the qualifications. With human resource planning, prospective employees can be prepared who have the potential to occupy manager positions in the future. (Anwar, 2005:5).

With Human Resources Planning, the management of the organization, in this case the madrasah, will be able to direct employees correctly so that their potential develops. Furthermore, the goals of the organization or madrasah in this case will be more easily achieved. Employees are the greatest asset to the progress of the organization, and improper handling by management will hinder the achievement of organizational or company goals and planning. Human Resources is the first and main function of Human Resource Management. Human resource planning can be described as a process that seeks to ensure that the right number and type of employees are available in the right place at the right time for the future, capable of doing things. Necessary for the organization to continue achieving its goals.

b. Organizing Educational Organizations in the Era of Globalization in Increasing Teacher Professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan

One dimension of humans is organizational creatures. He is known as an organizational creature because from birth humans cannot live alone without the help of others. In fact, the human physical structure itself is actually a system composed of sub-systems of body parts, all of which form a body system that has its own function and is perfectly organized to produce a perfect human figure. (Rahman, 2015:291). Therefore, management is often defined by management experts such as Richard L. Daft (2005: 8) as the process of achieving organizational goals in an effective and efficient manner through organizing planning, leadership and controlling organizational resources.

The role of human resources in organizations is very important because human resources are the managers of the system, so that this system continues to run, of course its management must pay attention to important aspects such as training, development and motivation. In this case, human resources are used as management as an important indicator of achieving organizational goals effectively and vitally. Human resources are a very vital organizational asset, therefore their role and function cannot be replaced by other resources. HR in an organization must always be oriented towards the vision, mission, goals and objectives of the organization in which it is located.

Organizing concerns the preparation of a series of predetermined actions, so that they can be implemented well. Human resource management designs the structure of the relationship between work, human resources, and the physical factors that will be involved. Managers must be aware of the complex relationships that exist between one specific unit and other organizational units. This happens after passing the planning stage, or a series of activities have been prepared. The next step is the implementation of these activities which must be organized. Organizations are a tool for achieving goals effectively because organizational functions must have a division of tasks and responsibilities for each person (employee) who carries out activities. Organizing is the process of dividing work into smaller tasks, assigning these tasks to people according to their abilities, and allocating resources and coordinating them in order to effectively achieve organizational goals.

c. Implementation of Educational Organizations in the Era of Globalization in Increasing Teacher Professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan

Implementation is identical to the driving function, namely describing how managers direct and influence subordinates, how other people carry out essential tasks by creating a pleasant atmosphere for collaboration. (Suegito, 2013:62) Implementation is implementing the process of leadership, guidance and providing motivation to workers so that they can work effectively and efficiently in achieving goals as well as providing routine tasks and explanations regarding the work they are part of and explaining the policies set out. Implementation function here is an effort to create a climate of cooperation among program implementing staff so that organizational goals can be achieved effectively and efficiently. The actuation function cannot be separated from other management functions.

The driving and implementing functions in other terms are actuating (giving guidance), motivating (generating motivation), directing (giving direction), influencing (influencing) and commanding (giving commands or commands). (Wukir 2013:33). Meanwhile, in this case there are several implementation principles as stated by Muninjaya (2004: 220) as follows:

- 1) Treat employees as well as possible;
- 2) Encourage the growth and development of human resources;
- 3) Instill in humans the desire to exceed;
- 4) Appreciate good and perfect results;
- 5) Strive for justice without favoritism;
- 6) Provide the right opportunities and sufficient assistance;
- 7) Provide encouragement to develop one's potential.

d. Supervision of Educational Organizations in the Era of Globalization in Increasing Teacher Professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan

Supervision is the process of observing the implementation of all organizational activities to ensure that all tasks being carried out are in accordance with previous plans. (Sondan, 2011:76). The supervisory function here is to regulate activities so that the organization's activities can run according to plan. In addition, control is also intended to find solutions or solutions if obstacles occur in the implementation of activities. Supervision here is a process of control by a manager in the institution so that the management he carries out can take place according to the agreed guidelines.

The implementation of the strategy to overcome the obstacles above is by applying devotion values based on the Divine value system (theological, ethical, aesthetic, physical-physiological, logical and teleological). The performance of school principals in carrying out their duties and roles in educational organizations needs to understand and have the divine aspect as a foundation for actions and actions aimed at ensuring that all activities constitute sincere devotion to Allah SWT. This is in line with Sanusi's opinion (2017:35), these values are developed as follows:

- 1) Theological Values, all those carrying out tasks related to the implementation of the role of educational organizations must realize that there is no all-powerful power except the power of Allah SWT, and need to realize that all humans will return to Him bringing faith and sincere deeds. The essence of professional performance is sincerity because all work that is not accompanied by sincere intentions will be in vain before Allah SWT. By believing in the truth of theological or divine values, there will be a process of carrying out tasks that is full of responsibility, fun and calming.
- 2) Ethical values, implementers and stakeholders need to understand the values of their respective professional codes of ethics. These ethical values must be implemented in

words, attitudes and actions with noble morals, so that they become role models for students and the surrounding community.

- 3) Aesthetic values are values of beauty based on God that need to be applied by every administrator of an educational organization by appearing as a complete Muslim and Muslim woman. The value of beauty is applied in words and actions that reflect the beauty of Islamic teachings, it needs to reflect aesthetic values both physically and psychologically.
- 4) Physical-physiological values relate to the elements of dhohiriyah that can be seen and touched. All resources that support the implementation of educational organizations are physically healthy, strong and beautiful so that they can support the creation of enjoyable learning activities for students.
- 5) Logical value, which focuses more on the creative and innovative power of organizers and implementers of educational organizations to develop real work in improving teacher professionalism through the application of a logical mindset. This can be applied in the use of HR management.
- 6) Teleological value is the value of the benefits of implementing educational organizations so that they can increase their professionalism in the era of globalization.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusion

MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan in implementing educational organizations in the era of globalization uses HR management to improve teacher professionalism. The management functions used in management include planning, organizing, implementing and supervising. In practice, there are still many shortcomings so that not all existing teachers are able to adapt and have competence in the era of globalization. So educational organizations need to implement appropriate management to overcome this problem.

- a. Planning for educational organizations in the era of globalization in increasing the professionalism of teachers at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan, where the management of educational organizations, in this case madrasas, will be able to direct employees correctly so that their potential develops, especially in the era of globalization.
- b. Organizing educational organizations in the era of globalization in increasing the professionalism of teachers at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan in this case dividing work into smaller tasks, assigning these tasks to people according to their abilities, and allocating resources and coordinating them in order to effectively achieve organizational goals.
- c. Implementation of educational organizations in the era of globalization in increasing the professionalism of teachers at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan in practice providing guidance, generating motivation, providing direction, influencing and providing.

- d. Supervision of educational organizations in the era of globalization in improving teacher professionalism at MIS Thariqul Jannah Pangalengan here is to organize activities so that the organization's activities can run according to plan with the aim of finding solutions or solutions if there are obstacles to implementing activities.

2. Suggestion

Based on the conclusions above, in this case the researcher provides the following recommendations:

- a. Educational organizations need to improve the professionalism of teachers with more visionary qualifications, meaning that teachers must be able to develop in the era of globalization with goals for the future.
- b. MIS Thariqul Jannah needs to improve its HR management function again. This is expected to increase teacher professionalism in the era of globalization.

References

- 1) Ara Hidayat & Imam Machali, (2012). *Pengelolaan Pendidikan, Konsep, Prinsip, Dan Aplikasi Dalam Mengelola Sekolah Dan Madrasah*. Yogyakarta : Kaukaba.
- 2) Engkoswara, Aan Komariah. (2012) *Administrasi Pendidikan* .Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 3) Fathor Rachman. (2015) *Manajemen Organisasi Dan Pengorganisasian Dalam Perspektif Al-Qur'an Dan Hadith*. Vol.1 No.2.
- 4) Giddens, Anthony (1991) *Modernity and Self-Identity. Self and Society in the Late ModernAge*. Cambridge: Polity.
- 5) Griffin, R. W. (2016). *Manajemen Jilid 1 Ed 7*. Jakarta : Erlangga.
- 6) Prabu Mangkunegara. Anwar Prabu. (2005). *Sumber Daya Manusia perusahaan*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 7) Safril Mubah, Ahmad. (2015). *Isu-isu Globalisasi Kontemporer*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- 8) Sagala, Syaiful. (2013). *Konsep dan Makna Pembelajaran*. Bandung: Alfabet.
- 9) Salim. Peter, Salim Yeni. (2004). *Kamus Bahasa Indonesia Kontemporer*. Jakarta : Modern English Press.
- 10) Sanusi. A. (2017). *Enam Sistem Nilai Kehidupan*. Bandung: Nuansa Cendikia.
- 11) Steger, M. F., Kashdan, T. B., Sullivan, B.A., Lorentz, D. (2008). *Understanding the Search for Meaning in Life : Personality, Cognitive Style, and the Dynamic Between Seeking and Experiencing Meaning*. *Journal of Personality*. Vol. 76, No. 2.
- 12) Syarbaini. Syahrial. (2014). *Pendidikan Pancasila di Perguruan Tinggi (Implementasi Nilai-nilai Karakter Bangsa)*. Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia.
- 13) Sztompka, Piotr. (2007). *Sosiologi perubahan sosial*. Jakarta : Prenada. Undang-undang nomor 14 tahun 2005 tentang Guru dan Dosen.
- 14) Wayne Mondy and Joseph J. Martocchio .(2016). *Human Resource Management, 14th edition*, Pearson Education : London.